

Heat Capacity and Thermodynamic Properties of $\text{Sr}_2\text{MoCoO}_6$ and $\text{Sr}_2\text{MoNiO}_6$

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The heat capacity (C_p) of the system $\text{Sr}_2\text{MoMeO}_6$ ($\text{Me} = \text{Co}^{2+}, \text{Ni}^{2+}$) has been studied in the temperature range of 290-580 K. Anomalies in heat capacity were observed with a slight hump around 417 K and 452 K for $\text{Sr}_2\text{MoCoO}_6$ and $\text{Sr}_2\text{MoNiO}_6$, respectively. Since no structural, magnetic or dielectric transitions exist in the relevant temperature range, these transitions appear to be of electrical in origin.

COMPOUNDS with the general formula ABO_3 which crystallise in perovskite like structures have been extensively studied in view of their dielectric, magnetic and thermal properties. The perovskite structure has been found susceptible to wide variation in compositions from the ideal ABO_3 formula by substitution of either A or B with cations of different valency states. Investigations in this direction have been made on compounds of the type^{1,2} A_2MMeO_6 . X-ray, magnetic and dielectric studies³ have been reported on Sr_2MMeO_6 ($\text{M} = \text{Mo}^{6+}, \text{W}^{6+}$ and $\text{Me} = \text{Co}^{2+}, \text{Ni}^{2+}$). However, little information is available on the thermal properties of the above system. Besides, the transition temperature values reported by various techniques were found to differ appreciably. Since the calorimetric data are more precise and are hardly affected by trace impurities, heat capacity measurements of $\text{Sr}_2\text{MoMeO}_6$ ($\text{Me} = \text{Co}^{2+}, \text{Ni}^{2+}$) were made to examine their type and temperature of transition. The results are discussed in this communication.

Experimental

The requisite amounts of AnalaR grade constituent oxides (except SrO which was weighed in the form of SrCO_3) were mixed by milling under acetone in an agate mortar and air dried. The dried mixtures were pre-fired below 1273 K in a platinum dish, ball milled and again fired for 4-6 hr between 1473 and 1573 K in air.

The final products were analysed by X-ray diffraction using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) and were characterised as single phase with tetragonal symmetry at room temperature ($\text{Sr}_2\text{MoCoO}_6$: $a = 3.94 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 3.97 \text{ \AA}$; $\text{Sr}_2\text{MoNiO}_6$: $a = 3.92 \text{ \AA}$

and $c = 3.95 \text{ \AA}$) by comparison with ASTM data file. No extra lines due to any of the constituent oxides were detected within the sensitivity of the method.

The heat capacity (C_p) of the samples was measured in an adiabatic calorimeter which was calibrated using $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and ThO_2 as standards. Comparison of the observed data with NBS values indicated⁴ the accuracy to be about $\pm 2\%$ while the average scatter of the experimental values from their own mean was $\pm 1.5\%$. The measurements were done in the temperature range 290-580 K. In the neighbourhood of transition, shorter intervals of temperature (about 2°) were taken to study the detailed shape of the curve.

Results and Discussion

The experimental molar heat capacities were determined in the same chronological order as measured, to facilitate estimation of temperature increments in the measurements. Appropriate corrections were made for curvature to yield true differential heat capacities. Anomalies were observed with a slight hump around 417 K for $\text{Sr}_2\text{MoCoO}_6$ and around 452 K for $\text{Sr}_2\text{MoNiO}_6$, respectively (cf Fig. 1). The molar heat capacities, entropy and enthalpy of these compounds are given in Table I.

In compounds crystallising with perovskite like structure, the co-existence of magnetic and dielectric dipole ordering has been reported and the transition might arise due to magnetic (antiferro-para), ferroelectric (ferro-para) or structural (tetragonal-cubic) transitions.

The magnetic ordering in these compounds can be accounted for on the basis of indirect exchange interaction of the type $\text{Me}-\text{O}-\text{M}-\text{O}-\text{Me}$, as

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TABLE I—THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF STRONTIUM MOLYBDENUM COBALTATE AND NICKELATE

Temperature K	Sr ₂ MoCoO ₆			Sr ₂ MoNiO ₆		
	C _p J/mole.degK	H _T - H _{298K} J/mole.	S _T - S _{298K} J/mole.degK	C _p J/mole.degK	H _T - H _{298K} J/mole.	S _T - S _{298K} J/mole.degK
300	108.6	217	0.72	103.8	207	0.69
350	114.0	5786	17.9	108.4	5510	17.0
400	121.0	11610	33.5	112.8	11045	31.8
450	119.6	17769	47.9	127.5	16890	45.6
500	123.1	23836	60.7	119.4	22890	58.2
550	125.6	30053	72.5	122.3	28940	69.7

Fig. 1. Heat capacity (C_p) of Sr₂MoCoO₆ and Sr₂MoNiO₆.

..... Sr₂MoCoO₆
— Sr₂MoNiO₆

elucidated by Blasse⁵, the respective Néel temperatures being 80 K for Sr₂MoNiO₆ and 34 K for Sr₂MoCoO₆. The susceptibility of Sr₂MoNiO₆ indicated a peak at 71.5 K which was attributed⁸ to the onset of antiferromagnetic ordering and another at 503 K to structural transformation (tetragonal-cubic). Thus the transition temperature of 452 K for Sr₂MoNiO₆, observed in our studies, does not correspond to the reported value for the magnetic transition. It appears, therefore, that the anomalies in the heat capacities are not due to a magnetic transition.

Dielectric studies of these compounds indicated⁸ the absence of anomalies arising from ferroelectric origin in the relevant temperature ranges.

From X-ray studies, the structural phase transition temperatures were reported¹ to be 503 K and 593 K for Sr₂MoNiO₆ and Sr₂MoCoO₆, respectively. These values are higher compared to our heat capacity peaks (452 K for Sr₂MoNiO₆ and 417 K for Sr₂MoCoO₆). These compounds may be thought of as derived from SrTiO₃ by

substitution of Ti⁴⁺ by Mo⁶⁺ and either Co²⁺ or Ni²⁺. It has been reported⁶ that SrTiO₃ undergoes a structural transition from tetragonal to cubic at 110 K. But heat capacity measurements showed⁷ no anomaly around this temperature. Substitution of Ti⁴⁺ by Ni²⁺ or Co²⁺ and Mo⁶⁺ having almost the same ionic radii may be expected to lead to a phase transition similar to that observed in SrTiO₃. Thus, heat capacity anomalies do not seem to correspond to structural phase transitions.

In view of the above, the possibility of the transition being electrical in origin may now be considered. The electrical conductivity measurements⁹ indeed showed a break in the activation energy around 454 K for Sr₂MoNiO₆. This is in close agreement with our value of 452 K. It is believed that a similar explanation can be offered for the heat capacity peak in Sr₂MoCoO₆ although, as far as the authors are aware, no electrical conductivity data have been reported in the literature.

In conclusion, it may be stated that heat capacity anomalies were observed in Sr₂MoNiO₆ (at 452 K) and in Sr₂MoCoO₆ (at 417 K), respectively. These transitions are presumably electrical in origin, since the electrical conductivity of Sr₂MoNiO₆ also behaves anomalously around 454 K, while no structural, magnetic or dielectric anomalies exist in the relevant temperature ranges.

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